

Self-formation of dual-phase nanocomposite Zr–Cu–N coatings based on nanocrystalline ZrN and glassy ZrCu

P. Zeman^{a,*}, S. Haviar^a, J. Houška^a, D. Thakur^a, A. Bondarev^{b,c}, M. Červená^a, R. Medlín^d, R. Čerstvý^a

^a Department of Physics and NTIS - European Centre of Excellence, University of West Bohemia, Univerzitní 8, 301 00 Plzeň, Czech Republic

^b Department of Control Engineering, Faculty of Electrical Engineering, Czech Technical University in Prague, Technická 2, 166 27 Prague 6, Czech Republic

^c Bernal Institute, School of Engineering, University of Limerick, V94 T9PX, Limerick, Ireland

^d New Technologies – Research Centre, University of West Bohemia, Univerzitní 8, 301 00 Plzeň, Czech Republic

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ABSTRACT

A novel type of nanocomposite Zr–Cu–N material based on hard nanocrystalline ZrN and amorphous glassy ZrCu was prepared by atom-by-atom deposition using reactive magnetron co-sputtering. The elemental composition of the coatings was systematically controlled over a wide range, so that the stoichiometry of both phases was the same in all coatings and only phase fractions varied. Experimental results obtained using X-ray diffraction and electron microscopies were complemented by thirteen ab-initio simulations for the same coating compositions. We found that the structure of the as-deposited Zr–Cu–N coatings undergoes a gradual transition from an amorphous to nanograined and finally to nanocolumnar structure. When ZrN fraction exceeds 20 mol.%, both phases exhibit the tendency for spontaneous segregation even without heating, forming a heterogenous dual-phase nanocomposite structure. At approximately 50 mol.% ZrN, the ZrN nanocrystals enveloped by a relatively thin amorphous ZrCu phase reach an optimum size (3–5 nm), resulting in a maximum enhancement of hardness by 38 % compared to the rule of mixture. For ZrN fractions > 80 mol.%, hardness and plastic work fraction follow the trend proposed by the rule of mixture and the coatings with a lower hardness but a higher plasticity compared to the ZrN coating are prepared.

1. Introduction

Transition metal nitride (TMN) protective coatings with high hardness and wear resistance have become popular materials for many engineering applications where deformation is limited to a relatively small extent. However, when protective coatings are applied to compliant surfaces, it is also necessary that they are capable of absorbing strain energy without cracking or even breaking. Since TMN coatings are brittle ceramic materials, they deform predominantly elastically until the failure stress is reached. One strategy to enhance their toughness involves combining them with a non-ceramic phase in a heterogenous nanocomposite structure that allows them to absorb strain energy to a certain level via plastic deformation. However, since an increase in toughness is usually associated with a decrease in hardness, a balance between toughness and hardness needs to be tailored to the specific application.

Nanocomposite coatings based on the concept of combining a hard

ceramic phase represented by a TMN and a soft metallic phase represented by a crystalline ductile metal have been introduced by Musil et al. [1]. They successfully prepared dual-phase ZrN/Cu coatings by reactive magnetron sputtering and showed that their mechanical properties can be tailored by optimizing the Cu content [1–3]. Later, they also demonstrated that these coatings not only have enhanced mechanical properties but also antibacterial functionality at Cu contents higher than 10 at.%. In addition to this Zr–Cu–N ternary system, other ternary (Al–Cu–N [4], Mo–N/Cu [5]), quaternary (TiAlN/Cu [6], AlTiN–Ni [7], Mo–Cu–V–N [8]) or quinary (TiAlSiN/Cu [9,10], AlTiVN–Cu [11]) coatings based on the same nanocomposite design have also become of interest, for which the microstructure evolution, mechanical or tribological properties, or cutting performance have been investigated.

Here, we further explore the nanocomposite concept, which combines a hard ceramic phase with a soft metallic phase. An alternative to a crystalline metal is metallic glass (MG), an amorphous alloy that exhibits a glass transition. Due to absence of a regular crystalline structure and

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: zemanp@kfy.zcu.cz (P. Zeman).

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thus grain boundaries compared to crystalline counterparts, MGs possess high strength and high elastic strain, with plastic deformation occurring via shear band propagation [12,13]. Their mechanical properties and thermal stability also correlate well with the packing factor and presence of icosahedral clusters, in which the atoms are frequently arranged [14].

Recently, magnetron sputter deposition has been proven to be an effective technique for preparing MGs as thin films (TFMGs) [15–17]. This non-equilibrium plasma deposition technique, with very high cooling rates on the atomic scale at the substrate, allows TFMGs to be prepared with a much greater variety of compositions and solubilities than bulk MGs. They also exhibit enhanced plasticity and fatigue resistance due to their reduced dimension in thickness [18,19]. Consequently, the better balance of ductility and strength, along with the amorphous structure of TFMGs, provides a new opportunity to combine them with other ceramic materials, such as TMNs, in a nanocomposite structure and thus develop novel materials with unique properties.

Based on this concept, we introduce and synthesize a novel type of nanocomposite coatings that combines a nanocrystalline TMN phase and an amorphous MG phase. To our knowledge, no such phase combination in a nanocomposite structure has been reported in the literature so far. Therefore, this article represents the first study of systematic research dedicated to this type of material.

We demonstrate that through careful adjustments of the elemental composition of the coatings, a self-organized heterogeneous dual-phase nanocomposite structure can be achieved via a one-step process of reactive magnetron sputter deposition using four distinct sputtering targets, one of the key challenges of this work. Zirconium nitride (ZrN) is employed as the hard nanocrystalline TMN phase, while a zirconium copper alloy (ZrCu) serves as the amorphous MG phase. We systematically investigate the microstructural evolution using diffraction and electron microscopy techniques as well as ab-initio simulations. We aim to correlate this evolution with observed changes in surface morphology, hardness, and plastic deformation during indentation tests, all of which are essential aspects of our analysis.

2. Methodology

Ternary Zr–Cu–N coatings were synthesized by reactive magnetron co-sputtering technique using an AJA International (ATC 2200-V) sputter system. Prior to each deposition, the base pressure in a cylindrical process chamber was reduced to below 5×10^{-5} Pa using a vacuum system comprising a turbomolecular pump (1200 l/s) and a multi-stage Roots pump (27 m³/h). During the deposition process, a controlled gas environment of argon (Ar) and nitrogen (N₂) was maintained inside the chamber with a total working pressure of 0.53 Pa (4 mTorr). The Ar gas flow rate was kept constant at 50 sccm, while the N₂ gas flow rate was varied between 0.5 and 5 sccm to tailor the nitrogen content in the coatings.

Two unbalanced magnetrons were used, each equipped with circular, indirectly cooled targets measuring 50.8 mm in diameter and 6 mm in thickness. The Zr target (99.7 % purity) was powered by a direct current (dc) power supply (Pinnacle Plus + 5/5 kW, Advanced Energy), while the Cu target (99.99 % purity) was powered by a pulsed dc power supply (TruPlasma Highpulse 4002, Hüttinger Elektronik) operating in a high-power impulse mode. The average power density applied to the Cu target during each pulse was 1000 W/cm², and the negative voltage pulse duration was fixed at 200 μs. The deposition rates from the individual targets were controlled independently, by adjusting the dc target power of the Zr target and the average target power of the Cu target by controlling the repetition frequency. The accurate measurement of the deposition rates was carried out using a quartz crystal deposition rate monitor (SQM-160, Inficon).

Single-crystalline Si (100) substrates were used for the depositions and prior to each deposition they were subjected to ultrasonic cleaning in isopropyl to remove any contaminants. Then the substrates were

positioned at 150 mm from the targets on an unheated and radio-frequency (rf) biased (50 W) substrate holder and rotated at a speed of 40 rpm throughout the deposition process.

The elemental composition of the as-deposited coatings was determined using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) coupled with wavelength-dispersive spectroscopy (WDS). A SU-70 instrument (Hitachi) operated at a primary electron energy of 15 keV was used for the WDS analysis. For quantitative analysis, Zr, Cu, and nitrides standards were utilized, and a conservative error margin of 1 at. % was considered. The residual oxygen content in the volume of the coatings was between 2–3 at. % for all coatings. The cross-sectional characterization was also performed by SEM with same primary electron energy. For this purpose, a Si substrate was fractured at ambient conditions to enable imaging of cross-section of the coatings.

The structure characterization of the coatings was performed using X-ray diffraction (XRD) measurements. A diffractometer (X'Pert PRO, PANalytical) with Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.154187$ nm) was used, and the 2θ range of 20° to 80° was scanned using an ultrafast detector X'Celerator. The data evaluation was performed using the PANalytical software package HighScore Plus.

The microstructure of the coatings underwent examination through transmission electron microscopy (TEM) utilizing a Cs image-corrected microscope (Titan Themis, Thermo Fisher Scientific) operating at 300 kV. An energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX) microanalysis was conducted using four windowless SDD detectors (Super-X Detection System, Thermo Fisher Scientific). The preparation of TEM lamellae involved employing the focused ion beam (FIB) technique using a dual-beam system with a Ga + liquid metal ion source (NanoLab 660, Thermo Fisher Scientific). For the FIB fabrication, the acceleration voltage was set at 30 kV for rough operations, followed by 5 and 2 kV for final polishing.

The thickness of the coatings and the curvature of the coating/substrate couples were determined using surface profilometry (Dektak 8 Stylus Profiler, Veeco). Additionally, the residual stress was evaluated using the modified Stoney's formula. To characterize the mechanical properties of the coatings, including hardness, effective Young's modulus, and elastic recovery, load–displacement curve measurements were performed using a nanoindenter (TI 950 Triboindenter, Hysitron) with a Berkovich-type diamond tip. Multiple indents were made at a load of 10 mN, and the data obtained were averaged. The penetration depth-to-coating thickness ratio was kept below 10 %. To study deformation behavior under a high indentation load of 300 mN, a microindenter (H100 microhardness tester, Fischerscope) with the Vickers diamond tip was used.

Atomic force microscopy (SmartSPM, AIST-NT) was utilized to study the arithmetic average surface roughness and surface morphology of the coatings. The measurements were performed on a characteristic 5×5 μm² area of the coating using a silicon tip with a nominal radius of 10 nm, and the microscope operated in tapping semi-contact mode. The same setup was used for a detailed examination of the indentation imprint on the coatings.

The experimental results are compared with ab-initio simulations employing density functional theory (DFT) as implemented in the CPMD code [20]. The simulations were executed within a 64-atom periodic cell. The core atoms and inner electron shells were modeled using Goedecker-type pseudopotentials. For the valence electrons, their wavefunctions were expanded using a plane wave basis set, setting an energy cutoff at 50 Ry. Due to the amorphous nature and dimensions of the simulation cell, the calculations were limited to the gamma point, omitting other k-points.

In our simulations, we employed the liquid-quench algorithm [21] to emulate the dynamics following an energetic ion impact. This impact leads to the melting of a localized material region, consequently generating thermal spikes. The liquid-quench algorithm was executed in several distinct steps: (i) Initial mixing of atoms at 6000 K for 2 picoseconds (ps), which is significantly above the melting temperature,

thereby precluding any formation of stable bonds. (ii) Subsequently, the system underwent an exponential cooling process, reaching a representative preparation temperature of 450 K over a duration of 2 ps. (iii) This was followed by a period of equilibration at 450 K, lasting another 2 ps. (iv) Finally, we collected structural snapshots at the 450 K equilibrium state for 0.5 ps. See [22,23] for a previous successful usage of the same algorithm, including a justification of the time scale (for a system where Zr is also the heaviest element).

The bonding statistics were analyzed using bonding distance cutoffs corresponding to upper bounds of first peaks of partial correlation functions (4.000, 3.475, 2.850, 2.975, 2.275 and 2.000 Å for Zr-Zr, Zr-Cu, Zr-N, Cu-Cu, Cu-N and N-N, respectively). Bonding statistics of amorphous binary N-free ZrCu (Zr₃₂Cu₃₂ simulation cell) were calculated for comparative purposes using the same simulation technique.

3. Results and discussion

In this section, we present the results of the study and provide a comprehensive analysis and discussion of the data obtained during our investigation of a series of Zr-Cu-N coatings prepared over a wide range of compositions, particularly Cu and N contents, starting with a ZrCu alloy and ending with the composition corresponding to stoichiometric ZrN (see Table S1 in Supplementary materials). The intention of the study was to prepare dual-phase nanocomposite coatings with various fractions of the two binary phases. Therefore, the elemental composition of the coatings was systematically adjusted to match the stoichiometry of these two phases. Specifically, throughout the coating series, we maintained a constant Zr content while gradually replacing the Cu content with N. We assumed that during the deposition process, all dissociated nitrogen would react with the sputtered Zr atoms on the substrate due to the more negative mixing enthalpy of Zr with N than Cu with N (see the negative mixing enthalpy of Zr with N₂ as opposed to the positive one of Cu with N₂ in [24]). Simultaneously, a low nitrogen partial pressure in the deposition chamber will lead to insufficient nitrogen to completely react with all Zr and the remaining Zr atoms will then mix with Cu due to their negative mixing enthalpy [25] to form a ZrCu alloy.

How our strategy approached reality is shown in the following paragraphs. The Zr-Cu-N coatings are presented based on different molar fractions of the two phases, calculated based on their atomic composition measured by WDS and then normalized.

3.1. Structure, microstructure and surface morphology

Fig. 1 is a summary of XRD patterns that illustrate the evolution of the structure of the Zr-Cu-N coatings as the N content in the series and thus the molar fraction of ZrN increase. A binary ZrCu coating shows a typical XRD pattern with a characteristic amorphous hump, indicative of materials with atomic ordering limited to medium range. In our previous papers [26,27], we showed through differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) measurements that this material undergoes a glass transition at about 410 °C, followed by subsequent crystallization at about 452 °C. This proves that it is MG.

As seen in Fig. 1., the addition of 10 at.% N at the expense of Cu (20 mol% ZrN) has no noticeable effect on the shape of the amorphous hump in the XRD pattern. However, once the N content reaches 14 at.% (30 mol% ZrN), the shape of the hump becomes asymmetric. This change is made more legible by comparing the measured hump with the fitted peak (highlighted in orange) representing the ZrCu metallic glass phase. To accomplish the fitting, we used the Voigt function and employed peak parameters derived from the amorphous hump in the XRD pattern of the binary ZrCu coating. Notably, the peak asymmetry becomes even more pronounced at 20 at.% N (38 mol.% ZrN).

Upon increasing the N content to 22 at.% (44 mol.% ZrN) and even to 28 at.% (56 mol.% ZrN), distinct broad peaks emerge, clearly indicating the presence of the ZrN nanocrystals (PDF Card No. 00-035-0753). These nanocrystals have a size of a few nanometers, as confirmed by both the Scherrer equation and a HRTEM analysis, which is presented later in Fig. 5. Furthermore, as nitrogen is further incorporated, a transition in the preferred orientation from (200) to (111) and a reduction of peak width, especially of the (111) peak, occur. These phenomena are observed up to 40 at.% N (80 mol.% ZrN). For 45 at.% N (90 mol.% ZrN) and 47 at.% N (95 mol.% ZrN), the preferred orientation reverts back to (200), while the binary stoichiometric ZrN coating exhibits a strong (111) preferred orientation. Throughout the coating series, the fitted amorphous peak shows decreasing intensity, which is consistent with the decreasing content of the amorphous ZrCu phase.

The evolution of the structure described above can be related to changes in the microstructure of the coatings observed in SEM cross sections (Fig. 2), as well as in the surface morphology measured by AFM (Fig. 3). The microstructure of the binary ZrCu coating looks smooth and featureless at first glance. A careful examination, however, revealed fine striations in the microstructure. These features are typical when plastic

Fig. 1. XRD patterns of Zr-Cu-N coatings prepared with varying fractions of ZrN and ZrCu phases. All patterns have the same vertical scale. The fitted peaks in orange represent the ZrCu metallic glass phase. The dashed green lines correspond to the positions of the ZrN diffraction standard (PDF Card No. 00-035-0753). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 2. Cross-sectional SEM micrographs of selected Zr–Cu–N coatings with the indicated amount of the ZrN phase.

Fig. 3. AFM images of the surface morphology of selected Zr–Cu–N coatings with the indicated amount of the ZrN phase.

strain is released during fracturing of MGs. The identical striations were also observed for the coating with 20 mol.% ZrN (not shown here). All other coatings, distinguished by the amorphous hump in the XRD patterns, exhibit a fully amorphous-like, striations-free microstructure with an extremely smooth surface and low surface roughness below 0.5 nm. The surface roughness increases to 1.6 nm when the asymmetry on the lower-angle shoulder of the amorphous XRD hump is evident (the coating with 42 mol.% ZrN). This morphological change is an indication of the formation of very small ZrN nanocrystals, although they are not clearly visible in the cross-sectional micrographs of this coating.

Upon a further increase in the N content, even a minor variation in the composition of the coatings induces significant changes in the structure, microstructure, and surface morphology. Fig. 2 illustrates that the amorphous-like microstructure of the coating prepared with 44 mol.% ZrN contains features reminiscent of columnar-like structures. In this case, ZrN nanocrystals become more identifiable in the XRD pattern (Fig. 1) and the surface undergoes a notable transition from a smooth to an intriguingly heterogeneous morphology (Fig. 3). The surface now displays peaks of approximately 50 nm in height, interspersed with flat regions. These peaks are believed to correspond to the nanocrystalline ZrN phase.

At a ZrN molar fraction of 56 %, the coating assumes a distinctly columnar microstructure, and the amorphous phase is barely visible in the SEM cross-sections. It is assumed that the amorphous phase occupies the spaces between the columns. This is also supported by the fact that the columns do not extend throughout the entire thickness of the coatings, as clearly illustrated in Fig. 2 for the coating with 80 mol.% ZrN. The microstructure of this coating also exhibits an increased contrast between columns, indicating a decreasing amount of the amorphous phase. The surface morphology of the coatings with a dense columnar microstructure is characterized by a high density of peaks corresponding

to the tops of individual columns. The surface roughness does not exceed 10 nm for all the columnar coatings, including binary ZrN.

3.2. Nanoscale structure

To gain deeper insight into the nanoscale structure evolution associated with varying composition of the Zr–Cu–N coatings, a thorough TEM investigation was conducted on three specifically selected coatings, each exhibiting an XRD structure with a different level of crystallinity. Fig. 4 depicts cross-sectional dark-field (DF) scanning TEM micrographs with insets of selective-area electron diffraction (SAED) patterns of a $Zr_{52}Cu_{29}N_{19}$ coating with 38 mol.% ZrN, a $Zr_{49}Cu_{23}N_{28}$ coating with 56 mol.% ZrN and a $Zr_{50}Cu_{10}N_{40}$ coating with 80 mol.% ZrN. Complementing this, Fig. 5 presents high-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM) micrographs of the same three coatings in the cross-section.

All the TEM results are consistent with the findings from XRD analysis. Additionally, they provide further important details about the structure evolution. A blurry DF micrograph together with a diffused halo in the SAED pattern of the $Zr_{52}Cu_{29}N_{19}$ coating with 38 mol.% ZrN (Fig. 4a) show a highly disordered amorphous-like microstructure, corroborating the observations from the corresponding XRD pattern (Fig. 1). Remarkably, using HRTEM, we were able to unravel extremely small nanocrystals of 1–2 nm in size, comprising only a few lattice planes, as highlighted with a yellow overlay in Fig. 5a. These nanocrystals appear to be relatively uniformly distributed within the predominant amorphous phase.

The DF micrograph of the $Zr_{49}Cu_{23}N_{28}$ coating with 56 mol.% ZrN in Fig. 4b demonstrates the formation of a heterogeneous nanogained microstructure. The SAED pattern consists of distinct continuous diffraction rings, which all correspond ZrN lattice planes such as (1 1 1),

Fig. 4. Cross-sectional DF STEM micrographs with insets of SAED patterns of selected Zr–Cu–N coatings with (a) 38 mol.% ZrN, (b) 56 mol.% ZrN and (c) 80 mol.% ZrN. The indicated lattice planes in the SAED patterns correspond to the ZrN phase.

Fig. 5. Cross-sectional HRTEM micrographs of selected Zr–Cu–N coatings with (a) 38 mol.% ZrN, (b) 56 mol.% ZrN and (c) 80 mol.% ZrN. The yellow overlays indicate areas where the nanocrystalline ZrN phase was identified. The lattice fringes in Fig. 5b and 5c correspond to the ZrN (200) lattice plane with a distance of 2.29 Å. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

(200), (220), (311), (222), (400) and (331). Although the diffraction rings are continuous, the (1 1 1) and (200) rings are more intense in some directions, indicating a preferred alignment of the ZrN nanocrystals in these directions. The continuity of the rings implies a small size of ZrN nanocrystals, which is confirmed by the HRTEM observation presented in Fig. 5b. The nanocrystals reach a size of up to 8 nm (larger compared to the coating with 38 mol.% ZrN) and are surrounded by an amorphous phase. The lattice fringes in Fig. 5b correspond to the ZrN (200) lattice plane with a distance of 2.29 Å, as labeled in the inset of the figure.

Finally, the $Zr_{50}Cu_{10}N_{40}$ coating with 80 mol.% ZrN exhibits a well-developed nanocolumnar microstructure (Fig. 4c). The width of the columns is measured between 5 to 15 nm, reaching the height of a few tens of nanometers. Combining SAED (an inset in Fig. 4c) and HRTEM (Fig. 5c) results, one can draw the conclusion that the columns correspond to the growth of the ZrN crystalline phase. This also corresponds well to the XRD analysis. The less uniform diffraction rings observed in the SAED pattern confirm a larger size of the ZrN nanocrystals compared to the coating with 56 mol.% ZrN. The amorphous phase is a minority phase that fills the boundary space between the crystalline nanocolumns.

To further verify the formation of heterogenous dual-phase nanocomposite structure based on ZrN and ZrCu, we carried out a detailed EDS mapping for the $Zr_{49}Cu_{23}N_{28}$ coating with 56 mol.% ZrN. This allowed us to discern regions of different elemental composition at the nanoscale. Two EDS maps in Fig. 6 show signals from two different couples of selected elements for better legibility (encoding N in green, Cu in red, Zr in blue). However, it should be noted that the size of the ZrN nanocrystals (less than 8 nm) is considerably smaller than the

thickness of TEM lamella (approximately 50 nm). Therefore, each area in the EDS map displays the signal from a few phases, as being one behind each other in different depths. Despite this limitation, we can observe that the N-rich regions (green in the top EDS map) well correlate with the Zr-rich regions (blue in the bottom EDS map). That is, these regions are examples of where the ZrN phase is located. The most apparent ZrN regions are highlighted by solid circles. On the other hand, the dashed circles represent examples of regions, which are rich in both Cu and Zr (exclusively red in the top EDS map and a mixture of red and blue in the bottom EDS map). In summary, the EDS mapping supports the findings of XRD, SAED and HRTEM.

Based on all these results, we can conclude that the structure evolution of ternary Zr–Cu–N coatings is in very good agreement with Barna's structure zone model [28]. Although this model describes the effect of impurity on the growth of the main component of the thin film, it can be considered analogous in our case, where two immiscible phases contribute to the formation of the film.

When a binary ZrCu alloy is deposited, the structure is purely amorphous (glassy). Once a sufficient amount of nitrogen is present in the deposition chamber, the nucleation of ZrN nanocrystals is initiated. Since the molar, and thus volume, fraction of the ZrCu amorphous phase is substantial, the growth of the ZrN nuclei is impeded by the rapid coverage of their surface by the amorphous phase and the repeated nucleation takes place (the case of 38 mol.% ZrN). A microstructure based on very small, equiaxed, randomly oriented nanocrystals embedded in the amorphous matrix evolves. As the nitrogen content increases, and thus the molar fraction of the amorphous phase decreases, the ZrN nanocrystals have more time to grow or coalesce

Fig. 6. EDS maps for a Zr–Cu–N coating with 56 mol.% ZrN. Solid circles represent examples of regions rich in N in the top map and in Zr in the bottom map. Dashed circles then represent examples of regions rich in Cu in the top map and in both Cu and Zr in the bottom map.

uninterruptedly, and the microstructure then comprises larger nanocrystals surrounded by the amorphous phase. The orientation of the nanocrystals is still random without any texture evolution (the case of 56 mol.% ZrN). The structures formed in this compositional range are given by a combination of thermodynamics and kinetics. While the two phases nanocomposite is kinetically more difficult to form than a homogeneous structure, it does form because it is thermodynamically preferred: see the aforementioned enthalpies and the results of ab initio calculations in Sec. 3.3. Qualitatively speaking, the self-formation of the thermodynamically preferred structure is kinetically allowed by the kinetic energy of arriving atoms and their potential energy of ionization, in both cases enhanced by the HiPIMS technique used to sputter Cu. Quantitatively, even higher energy delivered into the growing films (e.g. by ohmic heating) could for some compositions lead to larger ZrN crystals and thinner ZrCu phase between them of course.

Once the ZrN phase predominates, the amorphous phase plays a less significant role and the structures formed are given more and more by the kinetics (nucleation rate and growth rate). After the formation of the primary ZrN nanocrystals on the substrate surface with random orientations, the competitive growth occurs favoring faster-growing crystal orientations. As a result, a microstructure with less or more distinct conical (V-shaped) ZrN nanocolumns evolves. Since the amorphous phase occupies grain boundaries, it limits their mobility, and the width and compactness of the columns are less than what would correspond to the case of a binary ZrN film (the case of 80 mol.% ZrN).

3.3. Atomic structure and bonding statistics

To corroborate the experimental observations of the structure evolution and disentangle the bonding in the Zr–Cu–N films, thirteen ab-initio simulations (see Table S1 in Supplementary materials) were performed for the same ternary compositions as studied experimentally (with only minor modifications in the number of atoms to ensure integer numbers of atoms of individual elements and an even number of valence electrons). All ab-initio simulations were performed using 64-atom simulation cells with atomic densities given by the corresponding weighted average of those of crystalline ZrN, Zr and Cu. The snapshots of atomic structures of ten selected compositions are shown in Fig. 7. The corresponding bonding statistics are shown in the top panel of Fig. 8, and they are complemented by bonding statistics of ideally segregated system (cubic ZrN+amorphous ZrCu) shown in the bottom panel of Fig. 8.

The bonding statistics of the actual Zr–Cu–N system and the segregated one exhibit the same trends and even almost the same quantitative values (see below for the most important exception). It can be seen that the numbers of Zr–Cu and Cu–Cu bonds are decreasing and the numbers of Zr–Zr and Zr–N bonds are increasing as the molar fraction of ZrN is increased (replacement of Cu by N). The concentration of Cu–N bonds is negligible, and there are no N–N bonds present.

Close examination of bonding statistics and snapshots of atomic structures reveals that there is a driving force toward segregation to ZrN zones and N-free ZrCu zones, and a non-monotonic evolution of the atomic structure of the latter. These phenomena are partially quantified in Fig. 9 in terms of the preference to form Cu–Cu bonds. First, the ZrCu (–based) materials with zero or low N content are homogeneous, both visually and in terms of a low preference to form Cu–Cu bonds. Second, an increase in nitrogen content leads to the formation of a mixture of ZrN and ZrCu zones, especially within the middle of the composition range. These two kinds of zones are interconnected via Zr atoms. Consequently, the ZrCu zones are not entirely homogeneous: Zr can be preferentially found on their surface guaranteeing the interconnection with ZrN, while leaving Cu-rich atomic cores inside. Thus, owing to the concentration of Cu atoms in a smaller fraction of the material, there is a steeply enhanced preference to form Cu–Cu bonds in the middle of Fig. 9 (41–63 mol.% of ZrN). This preference is the highest at 44 mol.% of ZrN ($Zr_{32}Cu_{18}N_{14}$), i.e. in the same composition in which one can visually observe the most significant presence of segregated Cu in Fig. 7. This can be correlated with the findings of XRD, SEM and SAED analysis, which confirm the transition from amorphous to nanocomposite Zr–Cu–N films (crystallization of ZrN) at more than 44 mol.% of ZrN. Third, further N incorporation (more than 50 mol.% of ZrN) not only leads to the crystallinity of ZrN, but also naturally decreases the size of ZrCu zones, which gradually become too small to distinguish the surface and the core. This decreasing potential to form Cu–Cu cores of ZrCu zones leads to a monotonically decreasing preference to form Cu–Cu bonds, once again shown in Fig. 9. Indeed, the actual number of Cu–Cu bonds (ZrN-rich part of the top panel of Fig. 8) decreases much more steeply than what would correspond to a fixed degree of segregation (ZrN-rich part of the bottom panel of Fig. 8). Fourth, let us point out that at the highest molar ZrN fractions (90 % to 100 %), the atomic structures of $Zr_{32}Cu_3N_{29}$ (not shown), $Zr_{32}Cu_2N_{30}$ and $Zr_{32}N_{32}$ (snapshots in Fig. 7 for 94 and 100 mol.%) show a presence of ordered arrangement of Zr and N atoms, i.e. fingerprints of the aforementioned experimentally observed crystalline structure. For these extreme compositions, the driving force toward crystallization of ZrN has been captured despite the short time scale of simulations.

3.4. Mechanical properties

The changes in structure and the formation of the dual-phase nanocomposite structure (schematically shown in Fig. 10) are reflected in the evolution of the mechanical properties of the Zr–Cu–N

Fig. 7. Snapshots of the atomic structures of Zr-Cu-N materials with a different amount of the ZrN phase. The structures are shown after doubling 64-atom simulation cells in both directions.

Fig. 8. Compositional dependence of bonding statistics of Zr-Cu-N materials for the simulated structures in Fig. 7 (top panel) and ideal segregated system cubic ZrN+amorphous ZrCu (bottom panel). The number of bonds is related to 64 atoms.

Fig. 9. Compositional dependence of the degree of Cu segregation, shown in terms of the (Cu-Cu bonds)/(Cu-Cu pairs) ratio. The values for ≥ 81 mol.% ZrN are not shown owing to a high statistical noise.

films. The hardness and plastic work fraction, measured over the whole composition range using nanoindentation, are shown in Fig. 11. Since an addition of 10 at.% N (20 mol.% ZrN) does not result in significant changes in the amorphous structure (see Figs. 1, 7 and 9), the hardness and plasticity are comparable to those of the binary ZrCu film. This indicates a more uniform distribution of N atoms within the amorphous network, without forming a distinct nanocomposite structure. Once ZrN nanocrystals begin to emerge, and the nanocomposite structure is formed (>20 mol.% ZrN), the hardness increases beyond the values predicted by the rule of mixture (depicted in Fig. 11 by a dashed line). We suggest the following reasoning of this behavior. Initially, the deformation localizes within the amorphous ZrCu phase through shear band propagation. Very small ZrN nanocrystals (1–2 nm) are believed to freely flow in the amorphous phase, while larger ones might obstruct propagation of shear bands.

Fig. 10. A schematic representation of the evolution of the structure of Zr-Cu-N coatings with a gradually increasing amount of the ZrN phase.

Fig. 11. Compositional dependence of hardness and plastic work fraction of as-deposited Zr-Cu-N coatings. Dashed lines correspond to the evolution of the displayed quantities according to the rule of mixture.

The maximum enhancement in hardness is achieved around 50 mol.% ZrN, wherein ZrN nanocrystals attain an optimum size (3–5 nm), meaning that only a relatively thin amorphous ZrCu phase envelops the surface of all nanocrystals (assuming for simplicity cubic crystals and the 50:50 M ratio corresponding to the 41:59 vol ratio, the thickness of the amorphous phase would be 35 % of the crystal size). In this composition, most nanocrystals are jammed, and the deformation primarily occurs through dislocation movement within the nanocrystals, impeded at grain boundaries filled with the amorphous phase. As a result, the strength and hardness are augmented, albeit at the expense of reduced plasticity (as evident in the local minimum of the plastic work fraction in the bottom panel of Fig. 11). This behavior has also been observed and extensively studied for ternary Ti-Si-N films based on a TiN/SiN_x nanocomposite structure, both experimentally [29–31] and theoretically [32,33].

Further reduction in the ZrCu phase fraction (>50 mol.% ZrN) gradually leads to the discontinuity of the amorphous grain boundary. ZrN nanocrystals begin to touch each other at specific points, allowing a limited dislocation propagation from one nanocrystal to another. Consequently, the increase in hardness is suspended, and the fraction of plastic work increases. For compositions exceeding 72 mol.% ZrN, both quantities clearly follow the trend of the rule of mixture. With ZrN nanocrystals surpassing 10 nm in size, ZrN grain boundaries prevail over amorphous boundaries, resulting in a completely jammed film structure. The deformation is governed by the dislocation activity within the ZrN nanocrystals, similar to pure ZrN. Note that the slightly higher hardness of the binary ZrN film might stem from a higher value of the compressive stress (~1 GPa) compared to that for all nanocomposite films (~0.6 GPa).

In general, the trends in Fig. 11 confirm that hardness is a measure of resistance of a material to plastic deformation, because its non-monotonic evolution is inversely correlated with the plastic work fraction.

The examination of indentation imprints provides further insights into the extent of the plastic deformation and its mechanism. Fig. 12 shows representative imprints of a Vickers indenter made at a load of 300 mN. The imprints correspond well to the described deformation mechanisms. For instance, the amorphous film containing 10 at.% N (20 mol.% ZrN) shows large, deep imprints with noticeable pile-ups with distinct steps associated with the occurrence of shear bands during plastic deformation. When shear band propagation is hindered by ZrN nanocrystals, imprints exhibit less pronounced pile-ups and shear band steps (38 mol.% ZrN). As the hardness enhancement reaches the maximum and the deformation mechanism undergoes the transition from amorphous-dominated to nanocrystals-dominated, the plastic deformation extends to a significantly smaller volume surrounding the indenter. Consequently, the imprints exhibit no pile-ups but instead reveal thin walls of raised material surrounding them, particularly notable at 44 and 56 mol.% ZrN. At higher ZrN fractions (80 mol.% ZrN), the character of the imprints becomes indistinguishable from that of pure ZrN.

4. Conclusions

We have demonstrated that a non-equilibrium process of reactive magnetron co-sputtering, based atom-by-atom deposition, enables one-step preparation of a novel type of Zr-Cu-N coatings. These coatings exhibit a heterogeneous nanocomposite structure comprising two distinct phases: nanocrystalline ZrN and glassy ZrCu. By systematically adjusting process parameters, such as the target power densities, repetition frequency, and nitrogen fraction in the gas mixture, we successfully controlled the elemental composition of the coatings so that the stoichiometry of the two phases remained the same as much as possible and only the fractions of the phases varied. Thirteen ab-initio simulations for the same compositions complemented the experimental work, confirming the tendency of both phases to segregate.

The structure of the as-deposited Zr-Cu-N coatings undergoes a

Fig. 12. AFM images of imprints made at a load of 300 mN on selected Zr–Cu–N coatings with a different amount of the ZrN phase.

gradual transition from an amorphous-like state to a nanograined and finally to a nanocolumnar structure. Up to 10 at.% N, the coatings exhibit a homogenous amorphous structure with properties comparable to a ZrCu TFMG coating. At a higher N content, corresponding to a ZrN fraction exceeding 20 mol.%, ZrN nanocrystals and amorphous ZrCu zones emerge, forming a heterogenous dual-phase nanocomposite structure. With increasing ZrN molar fraction, the ZrN nanocrystals grow in size at the expense of the amorphous ZrCu phase. In addition, ab-initio simulations revealed that the ZrCu zones are not entirely homogenous, especially between 41–63 mol.% ZrN, due to their interconnection with the ZrN nanocrystals via Zr atoms.

The self-formation of the dual-phase nanocomposite structure significantly impacts the mechanical properties and deformation behavior of the Zr–Cu–N coatings due to the synergetic effect of the two phases. The hardness reaches a maximum enhancement of 38 % compared to the rule of mixture at approximately 50 mol.% ZrN, concurrently accompanied by a reduction in plasticity. We attribute this behavior to the optimum size (3–5 nm) of ZrN nanocrystals enveloped by a relatively thin amorphous ZrCu phase, hindering dislocation movement out of the jammed nanocrystals. For higher ZrN fractions (>80 mol.%), the hardness and plastic work fraction follows the rule of mixture and nanocomposite Zr–Cu–N coatings with lower hardness but higher plasticity compared to the binary single-phase ZrN coating are prepared.

The achievements in this work contribute to expanding knowledge in the field of nanocomposite coatings based on hard and soft phases and open new horizons for their future application.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

P. Zeman: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **S. Haviar:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **J. Houška:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **D. Thakur:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Investigation. **A. Bondarev:** Investigation. **M. Červená:** Investigation. **R. Medlín:** Investigation. **R. Čerstvý:** Investigation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial

interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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